

CAREER TRAJECTORIES OF BACHELOR OF SECONDARY EDUCATION MAJOR IN SOCIAL STUDIES GRADUATES OF URDANETA CITY UNIVERSITY A.Y. 2017 – 2019

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative-descriptive research study conducted in the year 2021 aimed to determine the profile and employability of the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Social Studies graduates from 2017-2019 of Urdaneta City University, Philippines. It was participated by the 72 of 79 alumni through simple random sampling and used the data gathering instrument of the Commission on Higher Education for the tracer studies. Highlights of the findings include: majority of the graduates surpassed the Licensure Examinations at once but with no earned units in post-graduate studies; chose the program of studies because of strong passion and family influence; employed in a local jobs relevant to their undergraduate programs; not the peer and family influence but salaries and benefits are viewed as the biggest factor that make them find, stay, and leave the job; and were able to land in their first job one month after graduation through recommendations and walk-in applications using their eligibility and personality but resigned after one to six months. In addition, major courses in their curriculum are perceived to be highly relevant in their employment while elective courses and extension programs must be reassessed to enhance its relevance to their chosen program. Personal and communication skills and values like honesty, love for truth, perseverance, hardwork, and unity are seen as the biggest contributory for work application. Lastly, it also revealed that competent faculty members and reputation in licensure examination results served as the best assets of the college of teacher education while the participants suggest laboratories should be modernized more to enhance hands-on learning

experiences, and classrooms should be upgraded with improved ventilation to create a more conducive learning environment.

Keywords: *Employability, Tracer, Graduates, Social Studies, Teacher Education*

INTRODUCTION

The present system of education in the Philippines has gone a process of transformation for the past centuries. From a practical and informal education during pre-Hispanic period where men and women were taught about things that they should know in order to survive such as manipulation of tools for men like hunting and gathering, how to fish, how to cultivate crops, how to build a house etc. and how to do household chores for women, to the educational system brought by Spaniards which was focused on molding God-fearing Christians, to the reformation in the education brought by the Americans, and up to the present more liberated educational system and introduction of K-12 program, it can be viewed that education is given not as a privilege but as a right.

Education is very important for one's life especially if someone wants to have a good future or to succeed in life. Education brings a lot of doors and has many advantages. Having education helps someone to think, feel, behave in a way contributes to his/her success. It also develops human personality, thoughts, interpersonal relationships, and prepares people for life experiences. To make it simple, education significantly affect employment and work status which will, in effect, contributes to a decent living. In relation to this, good career, good status in society, and self-confidence are some advantages education may provide (Al-Shuaibi, 2014).

The 1987 Philippine Constitution also mentioned the importance of education. Thus, the government shall make interventions in making education accessible to all such as free public elementary and secondary including UNIFAST in higher education for all. With this, the Philippine government gives the highest allocation of budget to the Department of Education to cater the educational need of its citizens.

In the Philippine setting, as of 2015, the country has a total number of schools including the public that comprises 47,351 schools, elementary education has 38,620 schools, integrated has 225 schools (Ocampo, 2017). Education now including schools as a major institution, will help in mobilizing Filipinos in the country.

Taguiwalo (2015) also argued that the 1987 Philippine Constitution viewed labor as the primary social economic force of the country making the people as its greatest wealth. Therefore, the government should look upon on how Filipinos be mobilized by providing access to quality education.

However, according again to Taguiwalo (2015), three out of ten Filipinos are either unemployed or underemployed. This means that there is an insufficiency of needs to provide for families.

On the other hand, according to Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), over 72 million Filipinos (94.7%) in January 2020 were employed, only 5.3% are unemployed, and only 14.8 were unemployed. This result was based upon before the rising effect of Covid-19 pandemic. On the other hand, during the pandemic, the PSA also provided a data for employment rate in January 2021 in which unemployment rate rose from 5.3 (2020) to 8.7% and employment rate of 91.3% from 94.7% in 2020.

On the tracer study conducted by Mandigma et al. (2018), the DOLE offered 4.23 million job vacancies for both domestic and abroad in 2014 and 1.29M were hired for jobs and some employers were also demanding for higher qualifications for their employees.

Robinson (2000) mentioned various skills that an applicant must possess in order to be qualified for a job such as basic academic skills, higher-order thinking skills, and personal qualities. Basic academic skills includes reading, writing, science, math, oral communication, and listening. Higher order thinking skills includes learning, reasoning, creative thinking, decision making, and problem- solving. And lastly, personal qualities include responsible, self-confidence, self-control, social skills, honest, integrity, adaptive & flexible, team spirit, punctual and efficient, self-directed, good work attitude, well groomed, cooperative, self-motivated, and self-management.

In the study conducted by Mwelwa et al (2021) in Zambia, skills acquired by social science degree programs graduates are needed in the job market and viewed the relevance of their education to their employment.

Moreover, if someone thinks of his/her future, studying at university can give an advantage. Grades and skills acquired may be relevant to the employers. However, first class degree and relevant subject for the career someone wants will most likely be competing against others who have the same academic qualifications. It also mentioned that thinking about employability at an early stage will increase the chance of being successful in life (Future Learn, 2022). Albina A. and Sumagaysay L. (2020) verified in their tracer study from a state university in the Philippines that graduates perceived their course or program taken in college as relevant to their first job including the curriculum of their course taken.

The use of education taken in college enables the graduates to acquire essential knowledge, skills, and values which are fundamental to employability. Concerning this, the employability of the graduates of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Social Studies in the College of Teacher Education at Urdaneta City University was seriously questioned if the curriculum, academic skills, and strengths of the college have helped them in making them successful by finding a job related to the course/program they had taken. It is for this cause that the researchers sought to determine the employability of the

graduates of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Social Studies in Urdaneta City University.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents regarding the following:
 - A.. Personal data
 - a.1 civil Status;
 - a.2. sex;
 - a.3 year graduated;
 - a.4 date when LET was passed;
 - a.5 no. of LET attempts before passing;
 - a.6 no. of Failed attempts (if [still] failed);
 - a.7 advance studies attended after college;
 - a.8 reasons for pursuing advance studies; and
 - a.9 reasons for taking the course;
 - B. Employment data
 - b.1. employment;
 - b.2 reasons for being unemployed (if unemployed);
 - b.3 employment status (if employed);
 - b.4 nature of employment;
 - b.5 place of work;
 - b.6 reasons for accepting the job;
 - b.7 reasons for staying on the job;
 - b.8 reasons for changing the job; (if employed and with previous employment);
 - b.9 length of staying in the first job;
 - b.10 way of getting the first job;
 - b.11 length of time before landing on the first job after graduation; and
 - b.12 perceived importance of credentials in work application?
2. What is the extent of relevance of the curriculum in terms of:
 - a. course offerings and programs;
 - b. skills competencies; and
 - c. work-related values ?
3. What are the qualities of the College of Teacher Education which you considered as college strength(s)?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The quantitative-descriptive method of research was employed in this study. The descriptive method of research describes and interprets the information gathered on

specific conditions and problems. It is an investigation method in which it tabulates data. It can also be used to analyze, interpret, compare, and identify trends and relationships (Limos et al., 2017). In this study, descriptive research suited accurately because it describes the employment status and the relevance of the education of the graduates of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Social Studies at Urdaneta City University.

Subjects of the Study and Sampling Scheme

The subjects of this study were the 72 graduates of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Social Studies from academic year 2017 to 2019 of Urdaneta City University who were from the City of Urdaneta and its nearby places including graduates from outside the province of Pangasinan. The researchers used simple random sampling in search for the respondents of the study.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Year Graduated	No. of Graduates	Actual no. of Respondents
2017	31	27
2018	27	26
2019	21	19
Total	79	72

Data Gathering Instrument

The instrument utilized by the researchers was a questionnaire that was developed based on the objectives of the study. It was based on the questionnaire created by Commission on Higher Education - Philippines. Some parts of the given questionnaire were changed for the purpose of the study, thus, it helped the researchers to gather pertinent and necessary data from the respondents. Specifically, Part I of the instrument pertains to the profile of the respondents which includes personal and employment data. Part II was about the extent of relevance of the curriculum. And, Part III was about the qualities of the College of teacher Education that the graduates considered as the college's strengths. The researchers concerted the questionnaire into an electronic survey via Google form and sent the survey-questionnaire via *facebook-messenger* platform to gather the data needed for this study. Again, some parts of the questionnaire were purposely replaced by important and needed variables to be able to get the desired data from the respondents. The collected data were analyzed and interpreted objectively by the researchers.

Collection of Data

The researchers made a letter asking for the total number and list of all graduates to the registrar's office of Urdaneta City University. The researchers sought also permission from the dean of the College of Teacher Education to gather data from the graduates of BSE Major in Social Studies graduates in the year 2021, two to four years

after the graduation of the respondents. Upon receiving the approval letter, the researchers made a calendar of activities to facilitate the collection, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data in the same year. A survey-questionnaire was distributed online to the respondents and retrieved also after the administration.

Tools for Data Analysis

Appropriate statistical tools were used to treat specific problems and to come up with a valid interpretation of data.

Frequency and percentage were used for the profile of the respondents including the strength of the College of Teacher Education.

The formula to gather the data of the students are shown below.

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100\%$$

Where: p = percentage equivalent of each category

f = frequency of the respondents

n = total number of respondents

Average weighted mean was used in determining the relevance of the curriculum and the college strengths.

$$AWM = \frac{\sum_1^n f_1 x_1}{n}$$

Where:

AWM = Average Weighted Mean

f = number of respondents falling or belong to each bracket

x = point value classification on the assessment

n = total number of respondents

The data were further described using the scale shown below.

Point Value	Descriptive Equivalent	Mean Range
3	Very Relevant	2.34-3.0
2	Relevant	1.66-2.33
1	Not Relevant	1-1.65

The following are the interpretations of the response descriptions:

Very Relevant - has a great relevance to the graduates

Relevant - has relevance to the graduates

Not Relevant - has no relevance to the graduates

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?

1.1 In terms of Personal Data

As shown in Table 2, there are 72 total respondents of the study where 27 or 37.5% were graduates of Academic Year 2016-2017; 26 or 36.1% were graduates of Academic Year 2017-2018; and 19 or 26.4% of the respondents were graduates of Academic Year 2018-2019. On the other hand, 70 or 97.2% of the respondents are single and only 2 or 2.8% are married. This indicates that majority the social studies graduates from Academic Year 2016-2017 to 2018-2019 are still of without marital obligations possibly due to their relatively recent graduation and early career stage. This is supported by Fry (2010) who emphasized that college-educated young individuals are more likely than those without a bachelor's degree to have married by the age of 30, reversing long-standing marital trends.

In terms of date of passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers, majority of the respondents passed the examination in September 2017 which garnered 26.4% or 19 among 72 respondents. This is followed by 17 respondents or 23.6% who passed on September 2018, 12 or 16.7% from September 2019, 10 or 13.9% from March 2018, and 5 or 6.9% from March 2019. On the other hand, 8 or 11.1% of the respondents have pending LET because of Covid-19 pandemic and 2 or 2.8% did not yet take the LET.

In terms of number of attempts before passing the LET, majority or 56 of 72 respondents (91.8%) are first time takers which indicates the high quality of education whom the graduates availed when they were in college and only 4 (3.3%) have 2 attempts, 2 (3.3%) have 3 attempts, and no one attempted to take the LET for more than 3. On the other hand, only 7 (63.6) of the 72 respondents have once failed LET, 2 (18.2) have twice failed LET, 2 (18.2) have thrice failed LET, but no one has a more than 3 times failed LET.

Table 2. Profile of the respondents

Profile	f	(%)
Civil Status		
Single	70	97.2
Married	2	2.8
Sex		
Female	44	61.1
Male	28	38.9
Year Graduated		
2016-2017	27	37.5
2017-2018	26	36.1
2018-2019	19	26.4
Date when LET passed		

September 2017	19	26.4
March 2018	10	13.9
September 2018	17	23.6
March 2019	5	6.9
September 2019	12	16.7
With pending LET because of Covid-19 pandemic	8	11.1
Did not take the LET yet	2	2.8
Number of LET attempts before passing		
1	56	91.8
2	4	6.6
3	2	3.3
More than 3	0	0
Number of Failed attempts for LET (If failed)		
1	7	63.6
2	2	18.2
3	2	18.2
More than 3	0	0
Advance Studies		
Master of Education - Social Studies (With Units)	19	26.4
Master of Arts in Education - Social Studies (With Units)	1	1.4
Master of Arts in Education –Educational Mngt (with Units)	4	5.6
Other master’s degree (with Units)	4	5.6
Master of Education - Social Studies (With Diploma)	4	5.6
With no units in any master’s program	40	55.6
Reasons for pursuing Advance studies		
For Promotion	18	25
For Professional Development	53	73.6

The data also showed that majority of the graduates have no units yet in advance studies which garnered 55.6% or 40 out of 72. This is because they are more focused on finding a job first for them to be able to finance their advance studies. This is followed by 19 (26.4%) graduates who are currently enrolled in Master of Education major in Social Studies, 4 or 5.6% are currently enrolled in Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management, 4 or 5.6% pursued other master’s degree program, and only 1 is presently enrolled in Master of Arts in Education major in Social Studies.

However, 4 graduates or 5.6% of the respondents have already done with their Master of Education major in Social Studies. Moreover, 53 respondents (73.6%) pursued advance studies because of professional development while 18 (25%) enrolled because of promotion. The data showcased that the graduates are passionate to pursue learning continuously though still earning units and degree in the post-graduate studies. As revealed by Esquerro et al. (2020), self-realization, job stability, and the capacity to compete in the labor market were the main drivers behind the graduate students' decision to pursue graduate study.

Figure 1. Profile on the Distribution of the Graduates Regarding their Reasons for Taking the Teacher Education Course

As shown in Figure 1, majority of the graduates chose the program of study because of the following reasons: Strong passion for the profession (43 or 59.7%); influence of parents/relatives (38 or 52.8%); affordable for the family (26 or 36.1%); and prospect for immediate employment (14 or 19.4%). On the other hand, the respondents emphasized that their least reasons of choosing the program of study are: Opportunity for employment abroad (2 or 2.8%); No particular choice or no better idea (5 or 6.9%); High grades in the course/subject (6 or 8.3%); and Prospect of attractive compensation (7 or 9.7%). The results emphasized that rather than financial incentives or overseas job prospects, the majority of graduates chose their degree based on personal interest or passion and familial influence. This implies that family expectations and internal motivation influence career decisions more than outside economic variables. Personal desire to choose teaching profession is vital because as highlighted by Corpuz and Salandanan (2013), passion is one of the key attributions of being an effective teacher.

1.2 Employment Data of the Respondents

Table 3 showed that majority of the graduates are presently employed which gained 76.4% or 55 out of 72 respondents indicating a high employment rate among the graduates, while 15 or 20.8% are presently unemployed but with previous job suggesting possible job transitions or instability in employment, while 2 or 2.8% are currently unemployed and never been employed after their graduation highlighting a minimal group struggling to enter the workforce.

Table 3. Employment Data of the Graduates

Indicators	f	(%)
Employed/Unemployed		
Employed	55	76.4
Unemployed (with previous job)	15	20.8
Unemployed (never been employed)	2	2.8

Reasons for being unemployed

Advance further study	1	7.1
Family concern & decided not to find a job	5	35.7
Health-related reasons	4	28.6
No job opportunity	2	14.3
Did not look for a job	1	7.1
Lack of work experience	1	7.1
Government duties (SK, Kagawad, etc.)	1	7.1
Waiting for RQA	1	7.1
others	1	7.1

Employment Status

Regular/Permanent	18	29.5
Contractual	25	41
Self-employed	3	4.9
Casual	7	11.5
Temporary	4	6.6
Job Order	4	6.6

Nature of Employment

Business/Marketing	3	4.8
Computer/Office jobs	1	1.6
Education and Training	49	79
Engineering	1	1.6
Industrial	1	1.6
Military	1	1.6
Others	6	9.7

Place of Work

Local	61	100
Abroad	0	0

In addition, with the 17 unemployed graduates, both with and without previous jobs after graduation, the main reasons of their unemployment were mainly because of family concern and decided not to find a job (5 or 35.7%) indicating personal or household responsibilities as a significant factor, health-related reasons (4 or 28.6%) which may have prevented them from seeking employment, and no job opportunities (2 or 14.3%) implying that a small portion faced challenges in securing a job due to market conditions.

Moreover, with regards to the employment status, majority of the graduates revealed that 25 or 41% of them are contractual employees suggesting that temporary work arrangements are common, 18 (29.5%) have permanent or regular work indicating stability for nearly a third of employed graduates, 7 (11.5%) are casual employees meaning they work on an irregular or short-term basis, and 4 (6.6%) are from both temporary and job order category reinforcing the prevalence of non-permanent jobs, and only 3 (4.9%) are self-employed showing a small fraction who ventured into entrepreneurship or freelance work.

Furthermore, the data also revealed that majority of the employed respondents are in the education and training sector which gained 79% or 49 out of 63 employed respondents while 6 (9.7%) are in the other sectors not mentioned in the questionnaire indicating diverse employment paths, 3 (4.8%) are in the business or marketing sector suggesting a minor presence in corporate sales or management roles, while there is 1 (1.6%) employed respondent for each category of computer, engineering, industrial, and military.

Lastly, all employed graduates are working locally and no one is working in foreign countries which suggests either a lack of international opportunities or a preference for staying in the country.

The data affirmed by Mandigma et al. (2018) who argued that most college graduates wanted to engage in a work relevant to their course program they have taken while also job mismatch is still inevitable because of lack of job vacancies.

As shown on Table 4, majority of the respondents accepted their jobs because of salaries and benefits and the job is related to the course program earned which garnered 40 or 60,6 % for both categories suggesting that financial security and alignment with their field of study are top priorities when choosing a job, followed by career challenge (35 or 53%) indicating that many graduates value professional growth and development opportunities, related special skills (30 or 45.5%) suggesting that graduates preferred jobs where they could apply and enhance their expertise. While family influence garnered 15 or 22.7% which indicates that location and convenience influenced job selection for a portion of graduates, followed by proximity to residence (14 or 21.2%) indicating that location and convenience influenced job selection for a portion of graduates, peer influence (9 or 13.6%) showing that a small number of graduates were influenced by their friends' job choices, while 4 (6%) of them had unique personal motivations not covered in the survey.

Moreover, Table 4 also revealed that salaries and benefits was the main reason why the graduates stayed in their present job which have 64.8% or 35 among the respondents. This is followed by career challenge (30 or 55.6%), related to course or program of study (30 or 55.6%), related to special skills (20 or 37%), proximity to residence (10 or 18.5%), and peer influence (6 or 11.1%), while 14.8% or 8 of the respondents have their own reasons for staying on the job not mentioned in the questionnaire.

On the other hand, graduates chose salaries and benefits as their main reason for changing their jobs which have 67.4% or 31 from respondents reinforcing that financial incentives drive career moves. This is followed by career challenge (15 or 32.6%) and related to course or program of study (14 or 32.6%) suggesting that employees seek career advancement and relevance when changing jobs, and related to special skills (13 or 28.3%) meaning that employees might leave if they feel underutilized. While proximity to residence and family influence which both garnered 19.6% or 9 respondents indicate that location and family considerations sometimes contribute to job changes, and 5 (10.9%) of them are less likely to be influenced by peers to change their job, and 6

respondents (13.1%) have their own reasons for changing the job not mentioned in the questionnaire.

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of Graduates' Response Towards Reasons for Accepting the job, Staying on the First Job, and Changing Job.

Indicators	f	(%)
Reasons for Accepting the Job (Multiple response)		
Salaries and Benefits	40	60.6
Career Challenge	35	53
Related to special Skills	30	45.5
Related to course or program of study	40	60.6
Proximity to residence	14	21.2
Peer influence	9	13.6
Family Influence	15	22.7
Others	4	6
Reasons for Staying on the Job (Multiple response)		
Salaries and Benefits	35	64.8
Career Challenge	30	55.6
Related to special Skills	20	37
Related to course or program of study	30	55.6
Proximity to residence	10	18.5
Peer influence	6	11.1
Family Influence	8	14.8
Others		
Reasons for Changing your Job (Multiple response)		
Salaries and Benefits	31	67.4
Career Challenge	15	32.6
Related to special Skills	13	28.3
Related to course or program of study	14	32.6
Proximity to residence	9	19.6
Peer influence	5	10.9
Family Influence	9	19.6
Others	6	13.1

The data above highlighted that salaries and benefits were the main reasons of the graduates of accepting, staying, and also for changing the jobs. Dash and Islam (2024) found out that financial incentives and job security are interrelated and are key components of job satisfaction among the present generation especially Generation Z. And, this financial security is important among young Filipinos because as reflected in the study of Mandigma et al. (2018) which emphasized that, in the Filipino culture, to help mobilize their families, graduates are more likely to become bread winners after landing on a job after graduation such as giving financial support to their families which is why the data shown in the Table 2 that majority of the graduates are with no marital obligations because they are more concerned on their family obligation right after graduation. On the

other hand, graduates did not merely give emphasis on the influence of their families and peers on landing in their jobs.

Table 5. Distribution of Graduates in response to way of landing on their first job

Indicators	f	(%)
How long did you stay in your first job		
Less than a month	11	16.6
1-6 Months	19	28.8
7-11 Months	8	12.1
1 year to less than 2 years	13	19.7
2 years and less than 3 years	15	22.7
3 years and less than 4 years	6	9.1
How did you find your first job		
Responded to the advertisement	7	10.1
Recommended by someone	28	40.6
Information from friends	12	17.4
Job Fair or public employment service office	2	2.9
As walk in applicant	17	24.6
Family Business	1	1.4
Arrange by school's job placement officer	0	0
Others	2	2.8
How long did it take you to land your first job		
Less than a month	35	51.5
1-6 Months	17	25
7-11 Months	8	11.8
1 year to less than 2 years	3	4.4
2 years and less than 3 years	3	4.4
3 years and less than 4 years	2	2.9

As shown in Table 5, majority of the respondents stayed in their first job for 1-6 months (19 or 28.8%) indicating that many graduates left their first job quickly. Next in line are the 15 (22.7%) respondents who have gained 2 years and less than 3 years in their first job suggesting some level of job stability among this group, followed by 13 (19.7%) who are 1 year to less than 2 years in their first job, 11 (16.6%) are less than a month, 8 (12.1%) are 7-11 months, and only 6 (9.1%) have the range of 3-4 years stay in their first job indicating that long-term retention in the first job is uncommon.

The table also showed that 28 or 40.6% of the graduates found their first jobs through a recommendation by someone suggesting that networking and referrals play a crucial role in job acquisition. This is followed by 17 (24.6) as walk-in applicants indicating that self-initiative remains an important method for job seekers, 12 (17.4%) found the information from their friends, 7 (10.1%) responded to the advertisement showing that formal job postings still contribute to employment but are less effective than personal referrals, 2 (2.8%) for job fair/public employment service office suggesting that either these sources were less utilized, 2 (2.8%) landed on their first job with the reason not mentioned in the questionnaire, and 1 (1.4%) respondent found his first job because of family business indicating that very few relied on family enterprises for employment, while

none from the graduates found their first job through an arrangement by the school's job placement officer which may indicate a lack of effectiveness or engagement in career support services from their educational institution.

Moreover, 51.5% or 35 of the graduates landed in their first job for less than a month after graduation. This suggests that more than half of the respondents were able to transition quickly into employment, likely due to strong networks, prior job offers, or high demand in their field. This is followed by the 17 (25%) respondents for 1-6 months indicating that a quarter of the respondents still found employment relatively quickly but needed some time for job searching and application processes., 8 (11.8%) for 7-11 months suggesting a more extended job-hunting phase, possibly due to job market competition, skill mismatch, or personal circumstances, while 3 (4.4%) for each category of 1-2 years and 2-3 years and only 2 (2.9%) from the graduates landed on their first job within 3-4 years after graduation indicating that these graduates might have faced challenges such as limited job opportunities, further studies, or personal reasons.

With this, the data clearly showed that graduates are work-ready since they were able to immediately land on their first job within less than a month after graduation through, by majority, a recommendation by someone and as walk-in applicant that also, by majority, stayed for 1-6 months and 2-3 years in their first job. This trend suggests that early career employees frequently switch jobs in search of better salaries, career growth, or job satisfaction. As reported by Cordero (2017), 42% of Filipino fresh graduates quit their first jobs in less than a year, almost 40% of them landed in their first jobs through personal networks, 41% lack industry knowledge, 21% lack mentorship, 30% were not prepared for working life, and 32% had challenges with their employer.

Table 6. Frequency Distribution of the Graduates Regarding the Importance of their Credentials in Work Application.

Indicators	f	%
1. Reputation of the University	34	47.2
2. Reputation of the Program	28	38.9
3. Previous Work Experience	31	43.1
4. OTR	39	54.2
5. Personality	54	75
6. Field Study	23	31.9
7. PRC	47	65.3

Table 6 clearly yielded 75% or 54 of the graduates regarded personality as the most important credential in their work application suggesting that employers may prioritize soft skills, attitude, and interpersonal abilities over other qualifications. This is followed by the critical credential which is the PRC license (47 or 65.3%) indicating that professional certification is highly regarded, especially in regulated professions, Official Transcript of Records (39 or 54.2%) signifying that academic performance and credentials still play a significant role in employability, reputation of the university (34 or 47.2%), previous work experience (31 or 43.1%), and reputation of the program (28 or 38.9 %), while field study was given the least importance which garnered 31.9% or 23

among all respondents which means that while practical training is recognized, it is not as crucial as personality, licensing, and academic records in securing employment. Overall, the findings emphasized that while formal education and experience are important, employers place the highest value on personality and professional licensing when considering candidates. The findings supported Unsal and Caliskur (2004) who argued that personality of a person during the selection process in work application is regarded as important by the employers.

2. What is the extent of relevance of the curriculum in terms of course offerings and programs, skills competencies, and work-related values?

Table 7. Distribution of the Graduates’ assessments on the Course Offers/Program

Course Offers/Program	WM	Descriptive Equivalence
General education	2.81	Very Relevant
Content Courses/Major Subjects	2.92	Very Relevant
Professional courses	2.88	Very Relevant
Elective courses	2.47	Very Relevant
Undergrad Thesis/Special Topics	2.58	Very Relevant
Seminars	2.66	Very Relevant
Community Extension Program	2.53	Very Relevant
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	2.69	VERY RELEVANT

Legend: 2.34-3.00 Very Relevant
 1.67-2.33 Relevant
 1.00-1.66 Not Relevant

It is shown in Table 7 above that the curriculum received by the graduates is assessed by the respondents as highly applicable to their professional careers which garnered an average weighted mean of 2.69. This indicates that the graduates strongly recognize the value of their coursework in preparing them for employment. Specifically, major (2.92) and professional courses (2.88) rank highest, reinforcing their direct applicability to career demands. In addendum, the high relevance of general education courses implies that soft skills, communication, and foundational knowledge play a crucial role in workplace success. These results can serve as a basis for curriculum enhancement, ensuring that all course components remain aligned with job market expectations and evolving industry trends. As cited by Darling-Hammond (2000), compared to teachers who have had little to no preparation, those who have had more preparation are more self-assured and successful with their students.

It is clearly shown in Table 8 that all the skill competencies that the graduates acquired in their college days are all described as “Very Relevant” to them and have helped them for their employment which garnered an Average Weighted Mean of 2.82. The results confirmed that graduates recognized these skills as highly important in their professional lives. Specifically, the following are arranged respectively in terms

Table 8. Frequency Distribution of Graduates Regarding Skill Competencies

Skill Competencies	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalence
Communication Skills	2.88	Very Relevant
Interpersonal Relationship	2.82	Very Relevant
Personal and Professional Growth	2.89	Very Relevant
Information Technology Skills	2.75	Very Relevant
Problem-Solving Skills	2.78	Very Relevant
Critical Thinking Skills	2.83	Very Relevant
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	2.82	Very Relevant

Legend:	2.34-3.00	Very Relevant
	1.67-2.33	Relevant
	1.00-1.66	Not Relevant

Of their weighted mean: personal and professional growth (2.89) received the highest rating indicating that graduates place significant value on self-improvement, career development, and lifelong learning in their professional success; followed by communication skills (2.88) and it is seen as critical skill suggesting that clear expression, active listening, and professional interactions are essential for career advancement; critical thinking skills (2.83) indicates that the ability to analyze, evaluate, and make sound decisions is recognized as a crucial factor in professional effectiveness and adaptability; interpersonal relationship (2.82) which indicates that strong interpersonal skills are highly valued, implying that the ability to collaborate, build relationships, and work well with others is essential in workplace success; information technology skills (2.75) which implies that the relevance of information technology (IT) skills suggests that digital literacy and the ability to use modern technology are key in today's workforce; and problem-solving skills (2.78) which means that the graduates acknowledged that logical reasoning and the ability to address challenges efficiently are vital in their professional roles. The study demonstrates how important a broad range of skills is for career success, including professional growth, communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving. Schools should concentrate on enhancing these skills to make sure that graduates are prepared for the needs of the labor market. With this, Heijke et al. (2002) argued that the competencies acquired by the graduates in their undergraduate degree could have a great impact in their lives as job applicant and/or as a worker.

The average weighted mean of 2.92 as shown on Table 9 indicates that the values which are earned and honed to the graduates are significantly regarded as highly critical for employment. Specifically, honesty and love for truth, perseverance and hardwork, and unity are recognized by the respondents as work-related values that are crucial for both career success and character development. The results imply that the college is successful in giving its graduates a solid ethical and professional foundation as these principles support leadership, personal development, and social responsibility in addition to workplace efficacy. The study of Baylor University (2011) revealed that employee

performance is positively correlated with their level of honesty and humility, as judged by their supervisor.

Table 9. Relevance of Work-Related values

College Strengths	Weighted Mean	Descriptive equivalence
Love for God	2.93	Very Relevant
Honesty and Love for Truth	2.96	Very Relevant
Punctuality	2.92	Very Relevant
Obedience to superior	2.88	Very Relevant
Perseverance and Hard Work	2.96	Very Relevant
Creativity and Innovativeness	2.94	Very Relevant
Courage	2.94	Very Relevant
Professional Integrity	2.95	Very Relevant
Love for Co-workers and others	2.82	Very Relevant
Unity	2.96	Very Relevant
Fairness and Justice	2.95	Very Relevant
Leadership	2.92	Very Relevant
Tolerance	2.85	Very Relevant
Efficiency	2.93	Very Relevant
Supportiveness	2.93	Very Relevant
Nationalism	2.90	Very Relevant
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	2.92	Very Relevant

Legend:	2.34-3.00	Very Relevant
	1.67-2.33	Relevant
	1.00-1.66	Not Relevant

Based in Table 10, graduates viewed the qualified and competent faculty members as the best strength of the college which garnered 81.9% or 59 from respondents. This means that graduates were very much satisfied with the quality of education that the faculty members of the college delivered. This implies that academic achievement is greatly influenced by the credentials, pedagogical approaches, and industry expertise of the teachers. Hence, the institution must invest on faculty development programs that will further enhance their competencies because they are regarded by the graduates as the greatest strength of the college.

This is followed by good passing rate in board examination (52 or 72.2%) which indicates that students of the institution are motivated also by how the college perform in the licensure examinations, well-organized internship program (46 or 63.9), enhancement program (44 or 61.1%), accreditation level (44 or 61.1%), students services programs (40 or 55.6), effective and efficient dean (39 or 54.2%), affiliated to DepEd (37 or 51.4%), and up-to-date books references (34 or 47.2%), LET review (34 or 47.2%) respectively.

Table 10. Graduates' Evaluation About the Strengths of College of Teacher Education of Urdaneta City University

College strength	f	%
Effective and Efficient Dean	39	54.2
Qualified and Competent Faculty	59	81.9
Well-ventilated Rooms	31	43.1
Well-organized Internship Program	46	63.9
Affiliated to DepEd	37	51.4
Enhancement Program	44	61.1
Up-to-date Books and References	34	47.2
Accreditation Level	44	61.1
Modernized Laboratory Facility	29	40.3
Good Passing Rate of Board-Exam	52	72.2
LET Review	34	47.2
Students Services Programs	40	55.6

On the other hand, well-ventilated rooms (31 or 43.1%) and modernized laboratory facility (29 or 40.3) earned the least strengths of the college. This means that the university may concentrate on improving facilities and offering additional resources to boost student learning experiences in order to further increase its reputation because these can also affect the teaching and learning process.

In support with the findings, Balanquit et al. (2023) found out that the qualifications of faculty members can affect the results of the Licensure Examination for Teachers among state universities and colleges in the Philippines, meaning the more faculty members who earned their doctorate degrees, the more that the Licensure Examination rating will increase. However, Ngozi and Halima (2015) revealed that inadequate laboratory facilities can hinder the academic performance of the students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1.a. Personal Profile. The BSE social studies graduates are dominated by female, single who are in early adulthood, and LET passers who were able to pass the examination at once. Majority of the respondents have no earned units in post graduate studies while others pursued advance studies for the reason of professional growth are either with units or with diploma. The findings also conclude that graduates had enrolled the college course/program because of their strong passion for the profession and influence of their parents/relatives while opportunity for employment abroad and no particular choice viewed as least reasons of the graduates for taking the course/program.

1.b. Employment profile. Majority of the graduates are employed and only 23% of them are unemployed (both with and without previous jobs after graduation). The

reasons of graduates for being unemployed were due to family concerns, personal choice, and health-related problem. On the other hand, majority of the employed graduates are casual and regular or permanent respectively to which the nature of their work are aligned to their undergraduate studies who are all working locally.

Moreover, these employed graduates accepted their first job after graduation because of salaries & benefits and its alignment to their program of studies. Also, salaries and benefits are the most reasons of the graduates why they stayed and why they decided to change their first job. On the other hand, peer and family influence did not affect much on why these graduates accepted, stayed, and decided to change their first jobs.

Furthermore, majority of the graduates stayed in their first job for a short period of time who applied for it as by recommendation by someone and as walk-in applicants respectively and were able to land in it for less than a month after graduation. However, least of the graduates stayed for 3-4 years in their first job provided that these respondents had graduated 4, 3, and 2 years ago, and least of the graduates also were able to change their first job after the said year duration. In addition, job fair and family businesses were also the least reasons of the graduates in getting their first job.

In terms of work application, personality and PRC license are regarded as the best factors that these graduates were hired while field study did not contribute much for their work application.

2.a. Curriculum. Content of the course/major subjects, professional courses, general education, seminars, undergraduate thesis, community extension program, and elective courses respectively were viewed as highly applicable for their professional career with a great emphasis on their majorship courses.

2.b. Skills. Personal and professional growth ranked highest as the most helpful skill in their employment that the graduates acquired during their undergraduate studies. Other skills like communication, critical thinking, interpersonal relationship, problem-solving, and information technology respectively also played vital role in their employability.

2.c. Work-Related Values. Values earned and honed to the graduates are significantly regarded as highly critical for the graduates employability. Values such as honesty and love for truth, perseverance and hardwork, and unity are recognized by the respondents as work-related values that are crucial for both career success and character development.

3. College strengths. Qualified and competent faculty members, and good board rating served as the best asset of the university while graduates observed that classrooms are not well-ventilated and some laboratories are not modernized yet.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the researchers recommend the following:

1.a. The college may introduce a post-graduate orientation before students will graduate for them to be encouraged to pursue their advance studies to increase their employability and career opportunities.

1.b. The college or institution must intensify the job-fair activities before or after graduation; increase the industry partnerships to open opportunities for the graduates; continue honing the skills and personality of the pre-service teachers; and continuously intensify the LET review programs. Also, employers must provide clear policies and transparent implementation of merit and promotion plan to attract employees to stay in their jobs.

2.a. The college must continuously improve the social studies curriculum and instruction under the teacher education through responding to the evolving standards and investing in faculty development programs. Additionally, elective courses must also be reassessed to ensure their relevance to the curriculum, while partnerships with local agencies must be enhanced to increase the impact of community extension programs.

2.b. The college should strengthen its efforts to develop the personality and communication skills of its students since these are the most needed factors that affect work application.

2.c. Nurturing values among students should continue to be given importance by the teachers especially honesty, love for truth, perseverance, hard work, and unity.

3. The college or institution should continue in upholding its reputation by ensuring that only highly qualified and competent teachers are hired to teach content, especially major courses, as this significantly impacts licensure examination performance. Additionally, laboratories should be modernized to enhance hands-on learning experiences, and classrooms should be upgraded with improved ventilation to create a more conducive learning environment.

4. Future researchers that will conduct similar to this study should have a broader scope.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Foremost, the researchers informed the participants about the nature and purpose of the study after being given permission by the administration to conduct the study. Consideration is vital to consider as it raises the aims of research wherein it desires to avoid something that will make this research inaccurate or less credible. Also, since research is frequently involved in cooperation with different people in their unusual behavior and institutions, it will help to develop values that are vital in accompanying

different people's trust and integration. The following ethical considerations were utilized in conducting this research:

Honesty. The researchers observed honesty in all forms of communication and in all sorts of data that helped the researchers and also the respondents to aim a fair and honest research study and not a subject for manipulation of the study.

Confidentiality. The researchers protected private and behind-the-scenes communications, all documents, all the data gathered were recorded, and other pieces of evidence entrusted to them.

Respect for Intellectual Property. The researchers give honor to all forms of intellectual property. The researchers employed the use of anti-plagiarism application software to ensure the proper citations, acknowledgment, and credits to the owner of such written forms used by the researchers to avoid plagiarism

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